

Adaptation to new audiences and digital narratives in the theater: case study in Campo de Gibraltar, Spain

Purpose:

This research explores the six public theatres in the Campo de Gibraltar region, Cádiz. The objective is to analyze their technological adaptation to new audiences and digital narratives.

Design/methodology/approach:

A mixed methodology was employed to gather quantitative and qualitative data, including two online surveys conducted between April 24 and May 10, 2023, with 257 participants from the public and eighty-nine scenic professionals, and six in-depth interviews with artistic directors and culture councilors.

Originality/value:

This study contributes value by comprehensively examining the perception of various key stakeholders in the field of performing arts regarding technological progress in the theaters of Campo de Gibraltar. By combining quantitative and qualitative data, it provides a comprehensive view of the situation and perceived needs in this domain.

Findings:

The study focuses on the theatre's materiality and the possibility of immateriality through digital technology. It reveals that the analyzed spaces are unequipped to meet the technical demands of artistic companies. Ninety percent of the shows are forced to reduce their technical requirements due to a lack of resources, and only 29 percent of productions offer multimedia content. This shortage of technical resources discourages the development of new digital narratives, hinders the theatres' technical renewal, and impedes new policymaking around performing arts. Although municipal theatres continue to provide in-person experiences supported by primarily analogue technology, a gradual interest toward new digital narratives is emerging. Exploring the state of playhouses and theatrical productions in Campo de Gibraltar illuminates the broader issue of the theatre's social role today.

Keywords: Municipal theatres, cultural industries, new narratives, communication technologies, audiences, performing arts

Summary: 1. Introduction, 2. Local theatres in Campo de Gibraltar, 3. Methodology, 4. Analysis and results, 5. Conclusions and discussion. References.

INTRODUCTION

Local theatre, the Stage, and the Digitalization of Theatre

This article deals with the situation of the local theatres of the Campo de Gibraltar region, Cádiz, exploring their materiality (e.g., tangible components, such as stage props, set design, and hardware) and the immateriality associated with digitalization and the use of technology in theatrical performances. These concepts are closely related to visual communication as they influence the aesthetic and perceptual aspects of the theatrical experience.

Enduring significant unemployment and poverty, Gibraltarians typically register low attendance at staged cultural events (Ministry of Culture and Historical Heritage of the Junta de Andalucía, 2021). Although the number of spectators has increased after the withdrawal of COVID-19-related constraining measures (INAEM, 2022), the depressed socio-economic situation, characterized by rising inflation, generates an appreciable erosion in theatre productions in this region (García, 2023). In addition, the widespread availability of global platformized audio-visual content –preferred by young people— is impairing local theatrical activity (Manchón, 2022).

By focusing on local public theatres in an underprivileged region of Spain, this research speaks of the critical role of the theatre in society, especially among deprived communities, and the challenges surrounding it. Previous studies demonstrate

(...) a rich multiplicity of social and educational possibilities for applying theatre to contexts of social vulnerability, including empowerment and development of critical awareness, promotion of personal and community development, construction of spaces

of recognition, development of empathetic attitudes towards human differences, and the recovery of silenced narratives (Massó-Guijarro, *et al.*, 2021)¹.

Art plays a crucial role in societal development (ESAEM, 2022). But the performing arts –which can involve music, dance, opera, puppetry, and drama— are like no other; they are ephemeral, visual, and staged each time anew in real-time for an audience (UNESCO, 2023). As a live social phenomenon, they require a relational process or theatrical *convivio* (Dubatti, 2011) that connects actors and audience in an imaginary space and time. There are no performing arts without an audience. The spectators influence every aspect of a theatrical performance by driving the content of the play or performance, the casting, the venue, the production, the performance's dates, and the meaning-making (Meisel, 2023). This participation in the show and the lack of distance from the stage during the performance enables a strong emotional response that creates “a mirror in which the community can look at and actively critically question itself”² (Massó-Guijarro *et al.*, 2021, 339). The theatre can be a liminal space where the lines between art and life become indistinct, which enables an emotional engagement between performers, play and audience and establishes communication conduits linking them (McQuaid & Plastow, 2017). The theatre can be a powerful tool to promote political, religious, cultural, and social dialogue (Ramírez, 2016). The theatre has always been a social endeavor, a meeting point where people interact among themselves and with the stage, developing relationships with others (Watchtower, 2020).

Namely, the structure of dramatic texts, unlike other forms of literature, is shaped by a collaborative production, direct visual and acoustic communication, and a collective reception. The creation of plays typically involves a writer, director, performers, and a technical production team that includes a set designer, makeup artist, lighting designer, costume designer, sound designer, stage manager, production manager, and technical director; sometimes, it includes too composer, dancers, and video designer, among others. The meaning-making process in the theatre requires the collaboration of the audiences, too.

Whatever the type of production, the center of dramatic action is the stage. The stage allows the creation of fictional worlds and the change of time and space perception (Parra, 2020). It is easy to picture the stage –also conceptualized as a *box*— as a universe where any idea can be enacted. A *stage box* is not only an architectural structure where different theatrical elements – such as costumes, lighting, sound, and the actors' and actresses' movement— are mobilized (Brockett & Hildy, 2014); it is also the framework where a dramatic action, whose design influences the work's reception and meaning, takes place (Souriau, 2008). Therefore, the stage is

¹ Scientific discussion on the social and educational uses of theatre has expanded significantly in the last decade. Our thematic analysis identified the documentation of a rich multiplicity of social and educational possibilities for applying theatre to contexts of social vulnerability, including empowerment and development of critical awareness, promotion of personal and community development, construction of spaces of recognition, development of empathetic attitudes towards human differences, and the recovery of silenced narratives. This review also uncovered a number of challenges and dilemmas inherent to the field, such as the question of power distribution in applied theatre processes or the complexities created by an instrumental vision of the arts.

² Theatre, as a live social phenomenon, calls for a relational and performative process or theatrical ‘convivio’ (Dubatti 2011), which involves the real-time connection between actors and audience to recreate an imaginary space and time. In AT shows, strategies are used to involve the audience in the scenic game, which narrows this ‘conviviality’ between the parties. Augusto Boal coined the term ‘spect-actors’ to refer to the new formula that breaks with the traditionally divided roles of spectator/actor (Silva and Menezes 2016). The opportunity for the audience to participate in the show — which is held in a familiar space with barely any physical distance between actors and audience — enables the audience to generate a direct emotional response. This also alters the passive receptive habits of the audience, creating a mirror in which the community can look at and actively question itself in a critical manner. Moreover, within certain approaches to AT, the boundaries between theatre and life itself are blurred, as they represent ‘dramatised images of the subjective realities experienced by each actor and by the collective as a whole’ (Cordero-Ramos and Muñoz-Bellerín 2019, 7). This can also facilitate intellectual and emotional engagement on the part of all those present in the performance (McQuaid and Plastow 2017) and, in turn, pathways of recognition for people in vulnerable situations.

not only a physical but also a conceptual space that can be used creatively to express ideas, emotions, concepts, and connections. Thus, it could be considered the intersection between architecture, literature (Jara, 2022), and communication.

The evolution of theatrical manifestations and their spaces has been intricately linked to technological advancements, creating tensions. As Auslander (2012) notes, the cultural understanding of what constitutes a live experience shifts in response to technological changes. In his seminal work, *Liveness: Performance in a Mediatized Culture* (1999), Auslander argues that the concept of liveness is historically contingent and shaped by mediatized forms. He highlights that the term *live* gained substance only with the arrival of recording technologies. This perspective challenges the anxiety surrounding perceived threats to live performance from technically enabled mediatization, asserting that both live and mediated experiences hold equal validity (Auslander, 1999). This discussion endures; for instance, in the post-COVID-19 era, theater critic McNulty (2021) would wonder “How to define theater in the digital era?” to respond, “I’ll know it when I see it.”

Historically, theater has embraced technology; for example, Baroque theater in Spain utilized machines to create storms and elaborate lighting effects with hundreds of candles. Today, theater continues to innovate through augmented reality and digital media, fostering immersive and interactive experiences that blur traditional boundaries. As González (2022) points out, contemporary performing arts increasingly favor hybridization, creating dialogues between multimedia and various artistic languages (Zorita, 2020). The emergence of digital technologies opens avenues for novel genres of theater and storytelling (Bhutipunthu & Konstanz, 2023; Furstenau & Mackenzie, 2009; Rogers, 2019; Ruecker, 2013). Artists across disciplines—writers, directors, musicians, and designers—collaborate with digital technologists to explore innovative storytelling methods (Rogers, 2019), while technological advances enhance audience participation and reshape theatrical narratives (Beltrán, 2020). This dynamic interplay between liveness and mediatization not only redefines performance but also enriches the audience's engagement with art in an increasingly mediated world.

The integration of digital technologies in theater has transformed the way performances are created, presented, and experienced. Digital theatre today often incorporates multimedia elements such as video projections, interactive interfaces, and augmented reality to create immersive worlds (Day, 2017). For example, some productions use binaural 3D sound technology and videomapping to enhance the theatrical experience (Day, 2017). Live streaming allows audiences to watch performances from anywhere, transcending geographical boundaries; this has democratized the theatre-going experience, making it accessible to many audiences (On The Stage, 2024). Augmented Reality (AR) blends digital content with the real world, enhancing the live theatre experience with interactive elements. This technology can overlay digital images, sounds, and other sensory inputs onto the physical world, creating a hybrid reality and encouraging audience participation (Matt, 2024). The combination of theatre and film on stage is valued, with the use of cameras to focus on actors, actors interacting with characters present only on video, and the augmentation of human bodies in dance performances through on-screen projections (Day, 2017). Hybrid theatre productions combine traditional live performances with digital technologies, offering several benefits. They allow theatres to sell unlimited tickets, as streaming options enable audiences to watch the performance virtually, which can enable theatres to transcend space (On The Stage, 2024). Hybrid theatre opens doors to innovative storytelling techniques and makes theatre more accessible, especially to younger, digital-native audiences and those who cannot attend live performances due to geographical or other constraints (Kolahal, 2024).

The COVID-19 pandemic led to widespread lockdowns and restrictions on mass gatherings, severely affecting live theatre performances and accelerating the digital transformation of theatre as auditoriums had to devise alternative methods to keep the industry alive (see e.g., Aranyosy, 2022; Brilli, Dunne-Howrie, 2022; Gemini, & Giuliani, 2023; Chatzichristodoulou et al., 2022). During the pandemic, digital theatre experienced a significant boom, with ticket sales increasing by 772% in Europe from 2019-2021, while regular ticket sales fell by over two-thirds during the same period (European Theatre Convention, n.d.). The pandemic prompted theatre companies to be more creative in applying digital technologies (e.g.,

Chen, 2002; Chountasi, Dafiotis & Sylaiou, 2021; Rixon, Brumpton & Morton, 2022). Hybrid theatre emerged as a practical approach to ensure the sustainability of theatre, combining live and virtual elements to engage audiences and maintain the art form (European Theatre Convention, n.d.), and blurring the lines between live and virtual theatre.

The integration of digital skills in local theater has become paramount for its survival, innovation, and reach (e.g., Webb & Layton, 2023). Digital skills are essential for various technical aspects of theatre production; for instance, theatre practitioners need proficiency in areas such as digital lighting, and video and sound design (Sullican, 2023). To adapt to new digital technologies, theatre professionals and students need structured training and development programs, including digital literacy and competencies (Mehr & Askarzadeh, 2024). Theatre organizations also need a comprehensive digital strategy to integrate digital technologies into their operations. This involves using digital technologies to innovate artistic practice, create and distribute content online, and analyze data to improve decision-making (European Theatre Convention, 2024). Digital technologies can make theatre accessible by streaming performances, using virtual reality, and creating interactive online content.

While offering innovative opportunities, digital technology in theater also presents significant limitations that reflect the inherent asymmetries and biases of these technologies. One major limitation is the reliance on technology itself, which can lead to technical issues such as poor connectivity, glitches that disrupt performances (Rajani, 2024), and digital divides. Additionally, digital platforms often lack the emotional interaction that characterizes traditional theater, diminishing the energy exchange between performers and audiences (Rajani, 2024). Furthermore, the algorithms used for content curation and audience engagement can perpetuate biases by favoring certain demographics, contents, or genres over others, which can marginalize diverse voices and narratives (Elcock, 2024). This phenomenon is evident in how streaming services prioritize popular content based on past viewing habits and promoted content, potentially sidelining unique or niche productions (Bardiot, 2020). These limitations highlight the need for a critical examination of how digital technologies shape theatrical experiences and the narratives they promote.

Besides, the artistic works produced under the influence of digital technologies circulate in new ways that traditional institutions do not quickly assimilate since, in general, their internal organizational structures, as well as their facilities, evolve more slowly than contemporary technological advances (Figueras, 2021). Through empirical research, this study analyses the six public theatres in Gibraltar to identify their challenges in incorporating digital technologies and how the visuality of digital media could contribute to changes in theatrical productions. To maximize the digital technology, rigging systems, digital lighting, digital video, digital sound, and direct communication stage-control cabins are considered necessary (Romero, *et al.*, 2013). These stage elements allow all sorts of effects to make the experience immersive for the audience by adding extra dimensions to performances (Rogers, 2019). In our analysis, we use these components to determine their design and how technologically advanced the theatres of Campo de Gibraltar are (Table 4).

Exploring the state of playhouses and theatrical productions in Campo de Gibraltar illuminates the broader issue of the theatre's social role today. This paper uses performing arts and theatre as synonyms for variety's sake. The article is organized as follows: first, we contextualize the situation of the local theatres in Campo de Gibraltar; second, we offer the methodology; third, we present the analysis; and fourth, we include the conclusions and a brief discussion. The authors elaborated the figures and tables except when a different source is indicated.

Local Theatres in Campo de Gibraltar

Campo de Gibraltar is in the extreme south of Andalusia. Due to its geographical location next to the Strait of Gibraltar, Campo de Gibraltar is a link between Africa and Europe; it has a heterogeneous and multicultural population, including immigrants from various parts of Spain and abroad (Rosón, 2022; Requena, 2021). A high level of unemployment characterizes the region; for example, the number of unemployed people in Cadiz at the end of 2022 was 21.12 per

cent, while in the Campo de Gibraltar region, it stood at 29.75 per cent (INE, 2022; Hildenbrand, Brown, 2021); meanwhile, the unemployment rate for Spain was 13%, more than double (INE, 2022). Besides, there is a high rate of school dropouts, which hinders access to decent jobs (Fenoy, 2021). Meanwhile, there is a high level of criminality related to theft, assaults, and drug dealing (López, 2023).

Despite the poor socio-economic situation, the area has significant cultural value due to its location and cultural richness. The area is at a crossroads; it is the shortest maritime link between the Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea and a gateway to Europe for the African continent. It borders British Gibraltar and Morocco. Beyond Mozarabic and Arab vestiges, Campo de Gibraltar exhibits theatre remains dating back to Roman times (Iniciatica Comarcal, 2023). The culture of theatre and performing arts is an essential element in its social and cultural development.

In the context of economic and social challenges, access to culture and promoting arts education become essential tools for social inclusion and development in the region. Currently, the area has six municipal theatres (Table 1) and several production companies. All the theatres in this study are publicly owned, and the shows that they offer depend on public funds from taxpayers' money. The municipal budgets of the departments of culture responsible for cultural programs and the maintenance of these theatres are included in the approved budgets of each municipality (Table 2). The ticket price for the shows performed in these municipal theatres, according to data collected on the websites that manage sales (i.e., www.tickettradas.com and www.giglon.com) ranges from free to 15€, that is, most shows are free or exhibit low prices to promote culture (Interviewees 1 & 2; see Table 4).

Table 1. Municipal Theatres of Campo de Gibraltar

Name	Construction Year	City/Town	Capacity (People)
Florida theatre	1944	Algeciras	600
La velada theatre	1988	La Línea de la Concepción	500
Millán picazo auditorium	2005	Algeciras	1,200
Juan Luis Galiardo theatre	2007	San Roque	500
Campo de Gibraltar auditorium	2010	La Línea de la Concepción	1,000
Alameda theatre	2011	Tarifa	280

Table 2. Local Budgets for Culture 2022

City/town	Theatre	Budget	Source
Algeciras	Florida Theatre & Millán Picazo Auditorium	1.876.126,80 €	sede.algeciras.es/PdfSede/PRESUPUESTO_2022_ALGECIRAS.pdf
La Línea de la Concepción	La Velada Theatre & Campo de Gibraltar Auditorium	755.634,00 €	www.lalineas.es/portal/index.php/ayuntamiento/concejalias-y-areas/economia-y-hacienda/presupuestos
San Roque	Juan Luis Galiardo Theatre	644.496,23 €	www.sanroque.es/sites/default/files/files_documentacion/2022/04/PRESUPUESTO%20A%C3%91O%202022%20%20.pdf
Tarifa	Alameda Theatre	624.294,21 €	https://www.aytotarifa.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Expediente-G2021_7794-Presupuesto-2022-Tarifa.pdf

Figure 1. Dimmed rods and lighting. Alameda Theatre, Tarifa.

Figure 2. Stage elements. Alameda Theater, Tarifa.

Figure 3. Florida Theatre, Algeciras.

Figure 4. Juan Luis Galiardo Theatre, San Roque.

After the crisis motivated by the COVID-19 pandemic, performing arts in Spain experienced a general increase during 2021 compared to the previous year; Andalusia is one of the autonomous regions that has registered the most significant growth (MCD, 2022). In Campo de Gibraltar in 2021, there were 161 shows, attracting 52,184 spectators, with a box office of 248,370 euros. However, neighboring Cadiz –just one city— held 1,093 shows for 3.97 million spectators (Table 3). Music was the most popular genre, for instance, with 85,644 spectators Cádiz in 2021, followed by theatre, with 65,684 spectators, and dance, with 10,846 spectators (IECA, 2022).

Table 3. Theatrical Works, Spectators, and Box Office in 2021

2021	Shows	Spectators	Box office	Expenditure per person
Spain	170,781	18 mill	278.38 mill €	15.40€
Andalusia	25,960	3.97 mill	46.45 mill €	11.70€
Cadiz	1,093	202,152	2.230.734 €	11.00€
Campo de Gibraltar	161	52,184	248.370 €	4.70€

Source: Ministry of Culture and Sports (2022) and Institute of Statistics and Cartography of Andalusia (2022).

The growth in the availability of digital, platformized content for cultural production and consumption has redefined the performing arts and generated a greater interest in innovative proposals. From this point of view, one could distinguish between three types of spectators. On the one hand, traditional audiences favor conventional theatre narratives and formats, which are

easy to consume and decode; on the other, some audiences are ready to experience new proposals in languages and formats that seek to innovate without changing the conventional codes of the theatre; finally, a minority audience seeks to experience emerging aesthetics and formats breaking with conventional theatre (Logroño Tormo & Llopis Goig, 2020).

Digital technologies have been used to improve theatre experience and reach a broader audience. Visual communication through digital elements can enhance the audiences' immersive experience and create more dynamic narratives within performing art productions, for instance, in musical performances (Bhutipunthu & Konstanz, 2023). In many locations globally, theatrical artists and spectators are experimenting with digital. Local productions are transcending borders through their digitalization (Ortiz, 2023; Sullivan, 2020). The employment of digital tools in drama can generate new personal geographies and intimacies (Gallagher *et al.*, 2020) and increase public engagement (Zhao *et al.*, 2019). Digital technologies can contribute to the sustainability of the theatre, too (Boh & Adoka, 2022). With these innovative technologies that allow asynchronous virtual realities, the question arises whether these new digital narratives can replace the stage and the physical closeness of performers and audiences in the performing arts.

That is why it is vital to analyze the technical factors of new creative productions and investigate how the stage can be transformed through virtual support (González, 2022). This research is focused on the need for digital visual and acoustic technologies in the stage in response to the demand for new audio-visual narratives in the towns of Campo de Gibraltar. These narratives include forms of communication based on digitalization, interactivity, and dematerialization, in which the traditional relationships between spectators and performers change. It may well be that our sense of the presence, power, and authenticity of theatrical productions derives not from treating the document as an indexical access point to a past event but from perceiving the document itself as a performance that directly reflects an artist's aesthetic project or sensibility and for which we are the present audience, (Auslander, 2018).

Thus, this study asks:

RQ1: What do performing arts professionals, council representatives responsible for the arts, and the audiences think about the technological progress of the theatres in Campo de Gibraltar?

RQ2: What is the perceived need for digitalization of local theatres, and what is the situation and design that restricts the use of digital media?

RQ3: How are the digital technologies applied to performing arts changing policy and practice in Campo de Gibraltar, and how could the visibility of digital media contribute to changes in theatrical productions?

Method

Secondary data were gathered from documents, technical *riders*, or accessible and public information that any theatre company can request to organize and adapt their stage productions. The database of the General Society of Authors and Publishers (SGAE) was consulted, too. A mixed methodology was used to collect primary data through two online surveys conducted over twelve days in 2023, one directed to audiences (257 people responded), and another with 89 stage professionals. Besides, six interviews with theatrical artists and culture councilors were conducted. Then, the information was combined in a complementary and integrative exercise following Hernández Sampieri (2014).

The mixed-method approach in the research on the technological adaptation of theatres in the Campo de Gibraltar region combines quantitative and qualitative methods to provide a comprehensive understanding. Surveys of audience members and scenic professionals gathered numerical data to identify trends, while interviews with artistic directors and culture councilors offered in-depth insights into stakeholders' perceptions and experiences. This approach benefits

from triangulation, which validates findings by cross-checking results, provides a broad overview through quantitative data and detailed contextual insights through qualitative data, and enhances the reliability and validity of the research findings.

Online Surveys Design

The online survey was designed following the guidance of ethical social research (Regmi *et al.*, 2016).

The two surveys were conducted between 04/24/2023 and 05/10/2023, using mobile devices through the Google Forms application. Survey number 1, entitled “Relationship between the audience and theatres”³, was addressed to the general population, both users of theatres and non-regular consumers of staged works. Survey number 2, entitled “Relationship between theatre professionals and theatres”⁴, specifically addressed professionals in the theatre sector.

The survey was designed to be easily accessible. For example, at a concert held at the Teatro Alameda, the public was invited to participate, the link was shared, and quickly spread in other towns Campo de Gibraltar region. The second survey, aimed at professionals, was shared with technicians and actors participating in the 2023 cultural programming of the Teatro Alameda, who in turn shared it with other theatre companies in the region. One of the authors is also an employee of the Department of Culture of the Tarifa City Council and is in contact with many theatre companies, which offered access to professionals in the performing arts, mainly at a regional and provincial level to distribute the survey.

Questionnaire one was aimed at the general population; meanwhile, questionnaire two focused on a selection of people related to the performing arts (Ruíz, 2012). The interest was to measure and understand social phenomena and processes in their complexity (Martínez-Salgado, 2012). Both questionnaires were structured into three blocks: the first collected demographic information, the second focused on factors that affect interest in and attendance at cultural events, and the third aimed at gathering factors that affect the need for more sophisticated technical equipment.

The phenomenon that is analyzed in this research is the need for digital technologies in local theatres of the town halls in Campo de Gibraltar, given the overall demand for new audio-visual narratives and two-way communication based on interactivity processes, where the relationships between users and performers change the traditional conception of the shows.

Interview Design and Justification

The data-collecting exercise includes interviews with civil servants with responsibilities over the theatres, including theatrical directors, actors, and actresses, selected based on their visibility, availability, and experience or role.

In-depth interviews were chosen for this research to gather detailed, nuanced insights into the perceptions and experiences of key stakeholders in arts management within the Campo de Gibraltar region. The use of in-depth interviews allows researchers to delve deeper into the experiences and perspectives of artistic directors and culture councilors, providing a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities faced by these theatres (Bryman, 2016; Creswell & Poth, 2018; Gummesson, 2000; Silverman, 2017). Semi-structured questionnaires were employed. This method involves a set of pre-defined questions or topics but also allows for flexibility and follow-up questions based on the respondents’ answers and is particularly suitable for arts management because it enables the collection of rich data that can capture the complex issues and contextual nuances associated with technological adaptation and digital narratives in theatres (Bryman, 2016; Creswell & Poth, 2018; Gummesson, 2000; Silverman, 2017).

We ask interviewees what they think happens and present these interpretations, paraphrasing Becker (1996), by talking to the people involved, verifying their statements with

³ *Relaciones entre públicos y los teatros.*

⁴ *Relaciones entre profesionales del teatro y los teatros.*

other available information, and giving them questionnaires to encourage them to say what they think. Six interviews were conducted with representatives of the cultural sector (Table 4). All the respondents –both in the surveys and interviews— are residents of Campo de Gibraltar. How accurately our portrayal of the technological innovation in Campo de Gibraltar theatres can be debated, as social scientists ascribe interpretations of the world to the people whose actions they observe (Becker 1996).

Table 4. Interviewees' Profiles

Interviewee	Sex/gender	Role	Profile
Interviewee 1	Woman	Culture Councilor, La Línea City Council	Civil servant
Interviewee 2	Man	Culture Councilor, Tarifa City Council	Civil servant
Interviewee 3	Woman	Actress, musician, and stage director, Instituto del Teatro de Sevilla	Artist/ stage director
Interviewee 4	Woman	Culture Councilor and stage director; director of the Artes Circenses Volátil school, Tarifa	Artist/lecturer
Interviewee 5	Woman	Stage director; member of the African Film Festival board, Tarifa & Tanger	Stage director
Interviewee 6	Man	Director of the Performing Arts Centre for the Development of Contemporary Performing Arts, Algeciras	Artist/ stage director

The interviews follow the guidelines of qualitative search. The interviewer and interviewees engage in a formal interview (Bernard 2006), and an interview guide was developed (Robert Wood Johnson Foundation 2008). Questioning is best used when the interviewee has in-depth knowledge of the subject (Bernard 2006). The interviews lasted from 30 minutes to 40 minutes. Permissions were obtained from each interviewee to use the contents of the interviews and surveys. Data obtained from the questionnaires and interviews were combined with the technical information of the municipal theatres for analysis. The municipal theatres studied are those located in Campo de Gibraltar (Table 1).

Analysis and Results

Online Surveys: First Survey with Audiences

The first survey was addressed to the general theatrical audiences. More than 66 per cent were women, three-quarters had higher education, and 42 per cent of all respondents were between 46 and 65 (Figure 5). The frequency of attendance at the theatre was from one to three times yearly in 54 per cent of the cases, followed by four to ten times a year (24 per cent).

Figure 5. Sociodemographic variables of performing arts audiences

Audiences say they base their decision to go to the theatre on their interest in the show's theme or plot (55.7 per cent of those surveyed). It should be noted that 60.8 per cent of the surveyed people say they like or are passionate about live performing arts (Figure 6); however, this contradicts the fact that performing arts are not the most consumed audio-visual content, including films and TV series, and videogames, with a total of 61.73 per cent (Figure 8).

Figure 6. Interest in the performing arts.

Figure 7. Preferred scenic artistic genre.

Figure 8. Knowledge and use of digital immersive and interactive products

The preferred theatrical genre is classical plays, with 50.5 per cent (Figure 7).

Also, 64.4 per cent of the respondents said they were aware of immersive and interactive cultural products; however, they also declared they were not consumers of such products (only 22.2 per cent were) (Figure 8). And 77.8 per cent of those surveyed said the content, messages, and plot are the most essential elements in a play. It is noteworthy that 36.4 per cent of them declared that the technical design and its adaptation to new narrative languages is the most significant element, indicating an interest in the technological aspects of theatre. In comparison, only 29.8 per cent of the people said the most critical aspect of theatre is who the leading artist is (Figure 9).

Figure 9. The most important element in a play.

Besides, 53.2 per cent said that new digital communication technologies can positively affect the theatre and that they thought the theatres are adapting to new formats, transmedia, and interactive narrative languages. In addition, 48.2 per cent of those surveyed said that the stage in theatres they know are not technologically adapted to the audio-visual needs demanded by the audience or that these spaces are adapting slowly to digital technologies (Figure 11). Meanwhile, 40 per cent thought that the performing arts are characterized by offering a face-to-face experience incompatible with virtual communication; the influence of digital technologies that allow asynchronous consumption is harmful, according to this group (Figure 10).

Figure 10. How new digital technologies affect scenic Works.

Figure 11. Technological adaptation of stage spaces based on public demand.

Online Surveys: Second Survey with Professionals

Of the performing arts professionals who responded to the survey, 39.8 per cent were female; most were between 46 and 65 (39.8 per cent), followed by 32.5 per cent of professionals between 36 and 45 (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Performing arts professional sociodemographic variables

More than a third of the professionals (34.64 per cent) said that the public decides to go to the theatre because of the play's publicity (Figure 13). This idea contrasts with the public's opinion in the first survey since 50.45 per cent of the people said they go to the theatre depending on the theme or plot of the play, followed by 22.9 per cent of the people who rely on the critics' reviews (Figure 13). This indicated, too, an overreliance of professionals on promotions and a lack of confidence in the audiences' ability to judge the play or rely on critics.

Figure 13. Reason for going to the theatre.

Regarding offering immersive or interactive cultural shows, 73 per cent of the professionals surveyed do not propose this type of content (Figure 14). Besides, 65 per cent of the professionals surveyed thought that the public does not demand this type of digital content in live productions since what is sought is the proximity to the artists and the stage offered by the theatre. However, 33 per cent of the professionals said that the public demands new interactive narratives, which is the reason they provide audio-visual content and real-time projections that interact with the actors.

Figure 14. Multimedia and immersive content offered in stage productions.

Regarding the technical equipment of publicly managed theatres in the eight municipalities of Campo de Gibraltar, only the La Velada, in La Línea de La Concepción, and the Juan Luis Galiardo, in the city of San Roque, have digital lighting systems and sound (Table 5).

Table 5. Campo de Gibraltar theatre equipment

Theatre	Flying/rigging systems	Lighting technology	Sound	Video	Communication Stage-control cabin
Alameda Theatre, Tarifa	Mechanized rods; manual & electrified	Analogue dimmers	Digitalized system	Analogue projector	Analogue
Florida Theatre, Algeciras	Mechanized rods; manual & electrified	Analogue dimmers	Digitalized system	Analogue projector	Analogue

La Velada Theatre, La Línea de la Concepción	Mechanized rods; manual & electrified	Digital dimmers	Digitalized system	-	Analogue
Campo de Gibraltar Auditorium, La Línea de la Concepción	Mechanized rods; manual & electrified	Analogue dimmers	Digitalized system	-	Analogue
Millán Picazo Auditorium, Algeciras	No rigging systems	Analogue dimmers	Digitalized system	Analogue projector	Analogue
Juan Luis Galiardo Theatre, San Roque	Mechanized rods; manual & electrified	Digital dimmers	Digitalized system	-	Digital

Comparing the Interviews with the Surveys

The interviews offer context and explanations for the ideas gathered in the two surveys.

First, there is a *difference between what the public said about what drives them to the theatre and what experts, practitioners, and civil servants declared* in the interviews and their survey. While most people stated they go to the theatre motivated by the play's topic and that they read the plays' reviews, most professionals and civil servants believed it is the fame of the artists involved and publicity that attracts people to theatre shows. That is, performing arts professionals and culture councilors agree that the main reason the public goes to the theatre is the notoriety of the actors and actresses, the play, and the marketing devoted to the show. For example, Interviewee 2, a culture councilor in Tarifa, said,

A cultural program that counts on famous musicians, actresses, and actors will result in an excellent box office (Interviewee 2)⁵.

This idea is shared by Interviewee 1, a Culture Councilor in La Línea de la Concepción, who said:

Unfortunately, it is celebrities who fill venues up (Interviewee 1)⁶.

Second, *there is a consensus about the lack of technical adequateness of the public theatre houses in Campo de Gibraltar* (Interviewees 3, 4, 5 & 6). The companies say that they have adapted to the theatres and space they work in, and not the other way around, with the consequent decrease in the technical quality of the original production (Figure 14).

Figure 15. Shows that reduce the technical rider due to the lack of equipment in public theaters.

⁵ “Una programación cultural realizada con músicos, actrices y actores famosos es garantía de buenos resultados en asistencia”.

⁶ “Desgraciadamente el famoso hace llenar los recintos”.

Professionals complain about the theatres' lack of adequateness, forcing them to adapt and reduce their *riders* (Interviewees 3,4, 5 & 6). A *rider* (a term of English origin) is a document that details the technical needs of an artist, band, or theatrical company to conduct their show adequately and that the theatre or promotor must make available. Interviewee 5, a stage director, for example, said:

The stages are poorly equipped. Although the municipal theatres are large, modern, and spacious at an architectural level, their technical equipment is insufficient to meet the demand of the technical *riders* of the companies that act in them (Interviewee 5)⁷.

The professionals interviewed agree that the theatres in this region are not sufficiently furnished (Interviewees 3, 4, 5 & 6). The publicly managed stages are not conditioned at a technical level to receive companies representing works with new technological narratives. Still, civil servants think the city councils and political leaders do not demand the generation of policies that technically revitalize the theatres. However, professionals say they increasingly base their productions on lighting and video projections, replacing sets and props to cut production costs (Interviewees 4 & 6). Interviewee 6 –Director of the Performing Arts Centre for the Development of Contemporary Performing Arts, Algeciras— said:

New communication technologies have greatly facilitated the shows' performances. (For example) video software and lights allow effects that were unthinkable not long ago; a single technician can manage several systems, which saves on personnel (Interviewee 6)⁸.

Meanwhile, Interviewee 4 noted:

The expensive and heavy decorations and props are being replaced by projections and new immersive audio-visual technologies on many occasions. This change allows for more inexpensive productions (Interviewee 4)⁹.

The numbers also confirm that, compared with municipal theatres in other Andalusian provinces, those in Campo de Gibraltar show deficiencies. Although they are modern buildings with good acoustics and visibility at an architectural level, there are deficiencies in technical equipment for sound, video, and lighting. The public, too, perceives theatres as spaces for conventional shows where there is no room for digital elements.

Despite thinking that the performing arts are in continuous technological adaptation, cultural managers and professionals said that, at present, marked by high inflation and the economic crisis, the digital devices employed serve to reduce production costs and not to innovate or expand the theatrical experience (Interviewees 4, 5 & 6). They also believe that, without the support of public institutions through the technical conditioning of spaces and municipal theatres, the new digital immersive productions will be complex for companies and productions with modest budgets to implement.

However, third, civil servants in charge of these theatres offered another perspective. Civil servants do not think it is essential to make significant updates without denying the obsolescence of the equipment in public theatres (Interviewees 1 & 2). For instance, Interviewee 1 said:

⁷ “Los escenarios están mal equipados. Aunque los teatros municipales son grandes, modernos y espaciosos a nivel arquitectónico, su equipamiento técnico es insuficiente para cubrir la demanda de los riders técnicos de las compañías que actúan en ellos”.

⁸ “Las nuevas tecnologías de la comunicación han facilitado enormemente las representaciones de los espectáculos. Por ejemplo, el software de vídeo y luces permiten efectos impensables no hace mucho; un solo técnico puede gestionar varios sistemas, lo que ahorra personal”.

⁹ “Las costosas y pesadas decoraciones y accesorios están siendo sustituidos en muchas ocasiones por proyecciones y nuevas tecnologías audiovisuales inmersivas. Este cambio permite producciones más económicas”.

Today, although it would be nice (to incorporate digital technology), it is not necessary to equip municipal theatres with digital technology to conduct immersive or multimedia events since there is no significant demand that requires modernizing the technical equipment with new emerging technologies (Interviewee 1)¹⁰.

Interviewee 6 further argues that public theatres are in better condition than private ones:

Despite the insufficient budgets to modernize stages, public theatres have better lighting and acoustic equipment than private ones; they are better conditioned to conduct large productions, too. Private theatres cannot compete with them (Interviewee 6)¹¹.

Summarizing, the politicians responsible for arts and culture justify the scarce technical equipment of public theatres based on the lack of demand for different shows. However, they also said that the technical equipment of these public spaces will be progressively renewed depending on demand (Interviewee 2).

Despite the apparent lack of demand for new shows, interviews with different performing arts professionals admit there is a growing demand for new things among young people. The interviewed professionals and politicians in charge of cultural affairs agree that ***a generational change in audiences demands new immersive or multimedia narratives*** without abandoning classical theatre, which offers proximity to the stage. However, this generational change is not equally distributed across genres. For example, Interviewee 3 –an actress, musician, and stage director— said:

There is a generational break in the public of music and dance shows. Meanwhile, in theatrical works, the audience is usually over 30 or 40 years of age (Interviewee 3)¹².

The survey indicated that the public of performing arts is primarily female (66.5 per cent), and most of the public is between 46 and 65 years old. However, most professionals are male (60.7 per cent), also between 46 and 65 years (40 per cent). There is a labor gender gap in these theatres, as men occupy most technical jobs. Although they use digital technologies, only 40 percent of professionals and the public belong to an age group characterized as not digital natives.

Although those interviewed agreed that there is a generational change, only 1% of the participants were under 18, and 12.6% were between 19 and 26 years old. These new generations are defined by having grown up in a social environment characterized by interactive digital communication that allows them to enjoy a convergent and transmedia culture. It can be argued that although 60.8 per cent of those surveyed indicated that they like or are enthusiastic about the performing arts, the audio-visual entertainment products they consume are offered on digital platforms, for example, TV series and movies (35.67 per cent).

For now, fifth, ***politicians and professionals are confident that digital technologies and narratives aided by artificial intelligence and virtual reality do not threaten the traditional performing arts and their workers***. Technicians, actresses and actors, scriptwriters, and other professionals are expected to coexist with new formats and virtual characters in the future. Interviewee 1 added:

Virtual reality and virtual intelligence (sic) are here to stay. Actors and technicians will adapt to these new technologies as they (theatre people) have always adapted to

¹⁰ “Hoy en día, aunque sería bueno (incorporar tecnología digital), no es necesario equipar los teatros municipales con tecnología digital para realizar eventos inmersivos o multimedia ya que no existe una demanda significativa que requiera modernizar el equipamiento técnico con nuevas tecnologías emergentes”.

¹¹ “A pesar de los presupuestos insuficientes para modernizar los escenarios, los teatros públicos cuentan con mejores equipos de iluminación y acústica que los privados; también están mejor condicionadas para realizar grandes producciones. Los cines privados no pueden competir con ellos”.

¹² “Hay una ruptura generacional en el público de espectáculos de música y danza. Mientras tanto, en las obras teatrales el público suele tener más de 30 o 40 años”

technological advances. They will know how to adapt and live with them (Interviewee 1)¹³.

When developing the cultural programs in their municipalities, civil servants in charge of the theatres said they do not receive proposals with new digital narratives and, therefore, there is still no established policy or discourse to put in place measures to guarantee that digital technology replaces live performances. This keeps programs full of traditional proposals. However, change might be looming over these theatres, whether there is awareness or not. The United States Film and Television Writers Union (WGA) was on strike from May 2 to September 27, 2023; among their demands, in addition to better labor conditions, they requested the regulation of artificial intelligence to produce content and reduce costs (Ramón, 2023). These pressures are expected to catch up with less advanced theatres, too.

The study shows that companies and stage productions mostly do not offer multimedia, immersive, or interactive digital content since the public does not demand it. 35,6 per cent of the public in the region does not know what multimedia, immersive, or interactive cultural products are (Figure 8). These data agree with the responses from civil servants in charge of the programs and the theatre houses. Despite this, Interviewee 2 admits that little by little, the face-to-face and the virtual are coming together on the stage, inviting spectators to experience new sensory and virtual events through multiplatform digital elements that have already appeared in stage projects, which were developed as alternative solutions during the restrictions of the COVID-19 pandemic. Interviewee 2 explained:

The public still does not demand virtual reality glasses or download an application when they go to the theatre. Despite this, new theatre proposals that emerged during the confinement are gradually re-emerging; these invite the viewer to participate and visit websites and social platforms where the shows can continue (Interviewee 2)¹⁴.

Table 6 summarizes the main findings emerging from the analysis of the survey's results and the interviews.

Table 6. The Findings Emerging from the Analysis

Main Ideas
1. Audiences said they go to the theatre because they are interested in the topic, and reviews guide them; meanwhile, civil servants and professionals believe big names and publicity drive the public.
2. There is a consensus about the lack of technical adequateness of the public theatre houses in Campo de Gibraltar.
3. Civil servants in charge of the public theatres do not think it is essential to make technical updates because there is no demand for it.
4. There is a generational change in the public that slowly demands new immersive or multimedia narratives.
5. There is the perception that digital technologies and narratives aided by artificial intelligence do not threaten the traditional performing arts and their workers' jobs yet.

Conclusions

¹³ La realidad virtual y la inteligencia virtual llegaron para quedarse. Los actores y técnicos se adaptarán a estas nuevas tecnologías como ellos, la gente del teatro, que siempre se han adaptado a los avances tecnológicos. Sabrán adaptarse y convivir con ellos.

¹⁴ El público sigue sin exigir gafas de realidad virtual ni descargarse una aplicación cuando va al teatro. Pese a ello, poco a poco van resurgiendo nuevas propuestas teatrales surgidas durante el confinamiento; estos invitan al espectador a participar y visitar sitios web y plataformas sociales donde las propuestas pueden continuar.

What do performing arts professionals, council representatives responsible for the arts, and the audiences think about the technological progress of the theatres in Campo de Gibraltar? Two conclusions can be drawn from the analysis.

- First, the results indicate the municipal theatres of Campo de Gibraltar are not equipped at all with the technical digital gear that could allow them to adapt to the new forms of visual communication and contemporary ways of cultural consumption. The study reveals that the six public theatres in Campo de Gibraltar are unequipped to meet the technical demands of artistic companies. Ninety percent of shows are forced to reduce their technical requirements due to a lack of resources, and only 29% of productions offer multimedia content. The study emphasizes the need for digital visual and acoustic technologies on stage to meet the demand for new audio-visual narratives. It suggests that digital technologies can enhance immersive experience, increase public engagement, and contribute to the sustainability of the theatre. However, the current infrastructure and organizational structures of the theatres in Campo de Gibraltar are not keeping pace with these technological advancements. Zoom theater, as described by Chen (2022), cannot be further from the reality of Campo de Gibraltar.
- And second, this fact has not to do just with the material situation of the theatres or their obsolete design but also with the lack of commitment and political will in terms of energy, funds, and political capital to achieve change.

What is the perceived need for digitalization of local theatres, and what is the situation and design that restricts the use of digital media? Here, we find three salient ideas.

- Contrary to what civil servants and professionals seem to think, this analysis does not determine that these theatre deficiencies result in a lack of interest from the audiences or that people do not demand innovation in the theatre. If the meaning of theatre is determined by plot, place, means of delivery, actors, and audiences generating a theatrical *convivio* (Dubatti, 2011) and the spectators shape every aspect of a theatrical performance (Meisel, 2023), this finding is truly relevant.
- Besides, the public's interest in theatrical topics and reliance on reviews detected in the survey could indicate that if more up-to-date shows in more contemporary formats were offered, the public might frequent the theatre more.
- Finally, the analysis suggests, too, that professionals and civil servants overseeing the financing of these endeavors should update their ideas about what people want.

How are the digital technologies applied to performing arts changing policy and practice in Campo de Gibraltar, and how the visuality of digital media could contribute to changes in theatrical productions? Here, three main ideas emerge from the surveys and the interviews.

- To begin with, at present, actors or actresses and their artistic proposals must be adapted to traditional lighting, sound, and projection equipment devices found in these theatres. The theatres of Campo de Gibraltar continue to be spaces where face-to-face experiences are offered, supported by conventional lighting and acoustics, to be shared synchronously as a community.
- Second, the civil servants responsible for their operation consider digital technologies to be, in some cases, a luxury they cannot always afford; this approach to innovation could compromise production quality, prioritizing flashy effects over narrative depth. Balancing technological innovation with the preservation of authentic, live theatrical experiences is essential to navigate these challenges. The integration of digital media has sparked a transformative theatrical evolution around the world, enhancing visual experiences through effects and dynamic lighting, enabling innovative set designs and augmented realities. This integration has revolutionized storytelling by enabling non-linear narratives, interactivity, and engaging diverse audiences. But this prospect is just embryonic in Gibraltar's theatres for the time being.
- Third, despite these shortages, according to the interviews, hybrid works are timidly being created where immersive and interactive elements are added to theatrical productions. Although the professionals and politicians interviewed believe that traditional theatre will continue to exist in its present form because of what they think is a scarcity of public

demand, it is to be expected that new digital narratives will be gradually displacing analogue props affording an interaction with spectators and a more innovative dramaturgy. Current digital technologies allow performers to interact with other virtual artists, potentially offering complexity on an emotional level and improving the plays' spectacularism (Poletta, 2019).

Discussion and Future Research

The study has several implications:

- The shortage of technical resources hinders the development of new digital narratives and impedes the theatres' technical renewal and new policymaking in the performing arts.
- The widespread availability of global platformized audio-visual content is impairing local theatrical activity. This trend, combined with the socio-economic challenges in the region, such as unemployment, is eroding theatre productions. The study highlights the importance of digital technologies in revitalizing local cultural production and engaging new audiences.
- The research underscores the critical role of theatre in society, particularly in underprivileged communities. The theatre can serve as a powerful tool for social dialogue and promoting dialogue. It can also be a space for empowerment and personal and community development.
- Finally, it explores how digital technologies are changing policy and practice in Campo de Gibraltar, highlights the importance of integrating digital media into theatrical productions to improve the relationship between the theatres and their audiences, and also questions whether new digital narratives can replace the traditional stage and physical closeness of performers and spectators in the performing arts.

This study has scope limitations and was not able to explore all the relevant issues surrounding the adaptation to new audiences and digital narratives in the theater. Avenues for future research include exploring strategies to upgrade the technical infrastructure and equipment in the public theatres of Campo de Gibraltar and funding mechanisms and policy changes needed to enable technological modernization of the theatres, as well as assessing the capacity building required for theatre staff to utilize new digital technologies effectively.

Another area of interest is how digital technologies can be leveraged to enhance audience engagement and develop new forms of theatrical narratives, including the preferences and receptiveness of different audience segments (e.g., traditional, innovative, and emerging) to digital elements in theatrical productions and the collaborative approaches between artists, technologists, and audiences to co-create immersive and interactive digital experiences.

It remains to be seen, too, whether digital technologies can improve the financial and social sustainability of public theatres in underprivileged regions without putting jobs at risk of alienating traditional spectators. The economic and social benefits of integrating digital tools to revitalize local cultural production and address socio-economic challenges should be further investigated.

Finally, how policy and governance frameworks can be adapted to support the digital transformation of public theatres is another exciting topic. Here, assessing the effectiveness of current funding models and cultural policies in enabling technological innovation in the performing arts is fundamental.

The theatre has constantly evolved, proving its social relevance. Stage companies' regeneration and commitment to digital technologies are necessary to attract younger audiences who are accustomed to the consumption of new narratives if the theatre is to survive the disappearance of older generations. For this, it is essential to adopt policies that encourage new multimedia and immersive formats to transform the theatrical stages into hybrid spaces where the virtual and immaterial coexist with direct and tangible experiences, which are currently non-existent in Campo de Gibraltar.

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